

Automatic Abbreviation Resolution for early modern Latin and Spanish TEI-Texts. A Regex-based Approach

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Abstract

Abbreviations were commonly used in early modern texts. Nowadays, this text phenomenon represents one of the biggest challenges during the complex process of manual scholarly correction and editing in our digital edition. This paper presents a regex-based automatic abbreviation resolution approach employing X-Technologies in our workflow: The School of Salamanca. A Digital Collection of Sources and a Dictionary of its Juridical-Political Language, with 116 works in selected prints from the 16th and 17th centuries, which are being published with high-resolution scans and complemented full text to enable easy access to primary sources, as well as, supporting online research with comfortable search functionalities.

Keywords

Early Modern Period, Spanish, Latin, Regular Expressions, Automatic Annotation, Abbreviation Resolution, TEI, XSL, Digital Edition

1. Introduction

The resolution and annotation of abbreviations of early modern Latin and Spanish texts is one of the main tasks of the project, *The School of Salamanca. A Digital Collection of Sources and a Dictionary of its Juridical-Political Language* [1]. The project aims to facilitate the reading of primary sources to the scientific community by offering both, a diplomatic and constituted view, rather than adapting the sources to current orthography. The resolution and annotation of this text phenomenon using regular expressions is part of an automatic correction and preparation process [2] to support and facilitate manual scholarly correction and editing before a work publication.

As part of these automatic corrections, we utilize a list-based automatic abbreviation resolution [3]. It uses two separated XML [4] lists with several abbreviations in early modern Latin and Spanish, which we have been gathering since 2018. Every item contains an abbreviation with its

respective expansion. Then, with an XSLT [5], all abbreviations found in a target text are automatically re-solved and annotated. For instance, in our Latin corpus, all suffixes \tilde{u} are resolved as *um*, as in *leg \tilde{u}* = *legum*. This transformation is very accurate since it only annotates abbreviations that match the exact item found in the list. However, this leaves many similar structures unresolved. Therefore, it was necessary to use a complementary approach.

Utilizing regular expressions to annotate and resolve abbreviations depending on their word structures has efficiently complemented the automatic list-based process mentioned above. Thus, with only one pattern, this regex approach not only resolves one word as *leg \tilde{u}* = *legum*, but also all the occurrences that share the same suffix \tilde{u} = *um*, as in *appellat \tilde{u}* , *adulterior \tilde{u}* , *cleric \tilde{u}* , etc.

This paper is structured in the following way: Section 2 provides general characteristics of the corpus in terms of its abbreviations and technical implications. After this overview, section 3 presents the potential of regular expressions and the regex-based approach in the context of our

digital edition. Section 4 shows the results. Finally, we present the conclusion and outlook in section 5.

2. Challenges and Context

2.1. Language

Early modern Latin and Spanish did not follow orthography standards as modern languages currently do. Thus, words vary and appear in our corpus with different spellings, and with special characters in disused today. This also affected a key phenomenon in our corpus, the use of abbreviations. From a pragmatic point of view, abbreviations enabled printers to save paper and ink, expensive items back then. Consequently, many words, regardless of their word class, were abbreviated. However, from a deeper perspective, abbreviations have their origins since Roman times with their stenographic systems [6]. Subsequently, they were common for centuries in European manuscript texts, so they were transferred to the printing [7].

An abbreviation is a lexical sign, in which a word is substituted for one or more of its components. Formally, it is constructed by an alphabetic component (the letter or letters that remain) and a symbolic component (the abbreviation sign or special characters) [8].

Capelli's *Lexicon abbreviaturarum* [6] explains in detail the structures of medieval abbreviations into six categories. From these, the following four are relevant for our corpus. First, abbreviations by truncation, when the first part of the word is written, while a special character replaces final letters as in *Aduertendũ* = *Aduertendum*. Second, abbreviations by contraction, when one or more of the middle letters are missing, but indicated by one special character as in *Dñi* = *Domini*, *Fernãdo* = *Fernando*, *Valẽcia* = *Valencia*. Third, abbreviation with their own meaning indicating missing letters, but without any connection to them, e. g. *p* = *pro*, *De^o* = *Deus*. Finally, and the most complex, abbreviations with variable meaning indicating missing elements in a word, but whose meaning is not set and varies *p* = *per*, *par*, *por*.

Table 1

Capelli's abbreviation categories relevant to the project The School of Salamanca.

Category	Abbreviation	Expansion
Truncation	Aduertendũ	Aduertendum
Contraction	Dñi Fernãdo Valẽcia	Domini Fernando Valencia
Own meaning	.p De ^o	Pro Deus

Noteworthy, abbreviations by truncation and contraction in our digital edition present variants, where the position of a special character changes or contains more than one in the same word. Moreover, a special characters ã, ã, ã, õ, ù might be resolved with m or n depending on the word structure and language. See Table 2.

Table 2

Abbreviation categories, their variants, and their respective expansions in project The School of Salamanca.

Truncation	Contraction	Both	Expansion
Aduertendũ	Aduertẽdum		Aduertendum
confirmaciõ	cõfirmacion	cõfirmaciõ	confirmacion
exemplũ	exẽplum	exẽplũ	exemplum
complementũ	cõplementum	cõplementũ	complementum

2.2. Printing and Transcription Errors

Printing errors and unclear parts (stains, wavy paper, etc.) from the original, and OCR/double-Key transcriptions typos can prevent automatic resolution and annotation of abbreviations. Words and even passages might appear either incomplete, misprinted, or mistyped. Currently, these issues are corrected manually, supported by automatic generated lists with potential error candidates.

2.3. Technical implications

One of the first challenges we faced, is the scarcity of tools for processing early modern texts. In most cases, they are based only in classic Latin [9], but not in early modern Latin and/or Spanish.

Moreover, Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools usually require plain text as input and produce similar output formats, which are not suitable for our workflow. Due to our text editing

process [10], the input and output formatting in TEI [11] play an important role in the whole workflow. Thus, the texts include all automatic and manual annotations and corrections added gradually. In turn, this allows providing users with a constituted and diplomatic view. Considering these details, abbreviation resolution and annotation is required in tokens, i.e., not only the character, but the complete word, with a detailed TEI markup. Therefore, an abbreviation such as *confirmaciō* should also comprise its expansion *confirmacion* as follows:

```
<choice>
<abbr>
  confirmaci<g ref="#charo0303">ō</g>
</abbr>
<expan>
  Confirmacion
</expan>
</choice>
```

These factors led us to develop self-tailored automatic solutions. In this specific case, the resolution and annotation of abbreviations depending on their word structure.

3. Resolution and Annotation of Abbreviation Structures with Regular Expressions

3.1. Why a regular expression approach?

Nowadays, regular expressions serve in several fields of NLP: Phonology, morphology, text analysis, information extraction, speech recognition, etc. [12] In terms of historical texts, it is employed to normalize text before further processing [13], or in our specific case as a digital edition, it supports text annotation and edition. Thus, regular expressions are a powerful tool that can be adapted to different contexts.

For decades, regular expressions and the algorithms to convert them into finite-state automata have been part of elementary computer science. However, they are recent and very useful for linguistic applications. Although, the syntax of a natural language cannot be described by a finite state, subsets of it such as names, dates, prices, etc., can be described by simple means [14]. Finite state formalisms have been also useful for the

description of linguistic phenomena for morphology, tokenization, and shallow parsing [15].

Therefore, if we handle the abbreviations as subsets of a natural language, we can employ regular expressions that define their structure in strings. All this de-rives in a finite state transducer that resolves and annotates them in the text.

3.2. Finding Abbreviation Structures with Regular Expressions

Having clear the structure of the abbreviations in our corpus, we defined the regular expressions to find them in the texts. Consequently, we found for Spanish 30 cases and for Latin 21. All these patterns, their scripts, documentation, and two cases of texts (input and output texts) are already published in a GitHub repository [16]. Most of the cases in both Latin and Spanish are abbreviations by truncation and contraction. Because of space, here are mentioned only few specific examples.

In Spanish, abbreviations by contraction with suffixes *ēdo* are resolved with *endo*, as in *pudiēdo* = *pudiendo*. With this pattern, words like *haziēdo*, *conociēdo*, *viēdo* are also found. The regular expression used to find these abbreviations is presented in Table 3.

```
pudiēdo = pudiendo
regex=" (' (\s) ([aA-zZñfç]+) (ē|ē|ē) (do) ([ ,; \(\)\]) ' )"
```

Table 3
Regular Expressions groups to find Spanish abbreviations with suffix *endo* by contraction

Regular Expression Group	
(\s)	Word boundary: white space
([aA-zZñfç]+)	Starting letters
(ē ē ē)	Special character, contraction
(do)	Closing typical letters
([,; \(\)\])	Word boundary: punctuation marks

In Latin, there are similar cases of abbreviations by contraction. For instance, abbreviations with contracted *ē* followed by the letters b, m, p are resolved with *em*. With this pattern, one also finds abbreviations like *exēplo*, *tēporis*, *tēpus*, *exēpta*.

```

exēplo = exēmplo
regex="{ ' (\s) ([æœęaA-zZfç]+) (ē|ē|ē|ē) (b|m|p) ([æaA-zZfç]+) ([, \?!\\(\)\*\+\+]+) '}"

```

Table 4

Regular Expressions groups to find Latin abbreviations by contraction with ē followed b, m, p

Regular Group	Expression
(\s)	Word boundary: white space
([æœęaA-zZfç]+)	Starting letters
(ē ē ē ē)	Special character, contraction
(b m p)	Closing typical letters
([æaA-zZfç]+)	Closing typical letters
([, \?!\\(\)*\+\+]+)	Word boundary: punctuation marks

It is important to mention, that word boundaries like punctuation marks and white spaces, as well as certain letters preceding or following a special character play an important role to avoid false positives and to determine how it is correctly resolved.

3.3. Resolving and Annotating Abbreviations with XSLT

So far, 3.2 presented some regular expressions to find abbreviations in a text. In order to perform an automatic resolution and annotation of the string found, we applied an XSLT and the instruction *xsl:analyze-string* [17]. This instruction evaluates if a given regular expression appears in the input text. If it is the case, the text is annotated as indicated in the script; otherwise, it leaves the input unchanged.

In this sense, we use a xsl:style-sheet (file) for Latin and one for Spanish. As we compile several cases, we employ one template per abbreviation case and add a mode for each one, so many searches are allowed in the same xsl:style-sheet.

Some of the texts in our corpus might contain small passages of languages different from Latin or Spanish, which are marked up previously. For this reason, every template exclude different languages from the main one using the expression *not(ancestor::*[@xml:lang[...]])*.

The following template serves as an example to show the process of one *<xsl:template>* resolving and annotating the abbreviations by contraction with suffixes *ēdo*:

This template selects only text in Spanish and assigns the mode="endo"

```

<xsl:template
match="text() [not(ancestor::tei:abbr or
ancestor::*[@xml:lang =
('la','grc','gr','he','fr','pt','it')])]"
mode="endo">

```

xsl:analyze-string instruction evaluates the regular expression. It is also divided in 5 groups.

```

<xsl:analyze-string select="."
regex="{ ' (\s) ^ ([aA-zZñfç]+) ^ (ē|ē|ē) ^ (do) ^ ([, ; \ ( \ ) ] ^ 5) ^ }" >

```

If the string is found, it is tagged as element <abbr rend="choice">

```

<xsl:matching-substring>
word boundary
<xsl:value-of select="regex-group(1)"/>

```

```

<xsl:element name="abbr">
<xsl:attribute name="rend"
select="'choice'"/>
<xsl:attribute name="resp"
select='#auto'"/>
<xsl:element name="abbr">
Abbreviation tagged <abbr rend="abbr">
<xsl:attribute name="rend"
select="'abbr'"/>
<xsl:value-of select="concat(regex-
group(2), regex-group(3), regex-group(4) )"/>
</xsl:element>

```

```

<xsl:element name="abbr">
Resolution <abbr rend="expan">
<xsl:attribute name="rend"
select="'expan'"/>
<xsl:attribute name="resp" select="'#CR
#auto'"/>
<xsl:value-of select="concat(regex-
group(2), 'en', regex-group(4) )"/>
</xsl:element>
</xsl:element>

```

```

<xsl:value-of select="regex-group(5)"/>
word boundary

```

```

</xsl:matching-substring>
<xsl:non-matching-substring>
<xsl:value-of select="."/ >
</xsl:non-matching-substring>
</xsl:analyze-string>
</xsl:template>

```

We work with texts in TEI-Tite [18] format, which are in an early edition stage [19]. This

allows easier readability and validation. The XSL-Transformation makes a copy of the input text and annotates there the abbreviations and their respective expansions with the following TEI-Tite structure:

```
<abbr rend="choice">
<abbr rend="abbr">[abbreviation]</abbr>
<abbr rend="expan">[expansion]</abbr>
</abbr>
```

Finally, it saves this copy as the output, which goes to further automatic edition steps and manual corrections. Input and output texts of two of our works, in both Latin and Spanish [20] [21], as well as the complete code is available under a GitHub repository [22]. It also describes in detail how to use the code and add more cases.

4. Results

Depending on the volume, its publication year, and its printing complexity, the number of abbreviations may vary. To quantify the performance of the regex-based XSL-Transformation, we gathered information from 10 of our published volumes, which were corrected by combining both, the list-based and the regex-based automatic abbreviation resolution.

The results yielded that these 10 volumes contain 31.935 abbreviations in total, from which 8.503 (26.62 %) were expanded by the list-based approach, and, 8682 (27.18%) by the regex-based approach. The remaining 14.750 (46.18%) were manually expanded.

Table 5.

Results of abbreviation resolution.

Abbreviation Resolution					
	Volume Code	regex-approach	list-approach	Manual	Total Expansions
1	W0006_Vol03	2199	2063	3293	7555
2	W0018	1213	309	695	2217
3	W0037_Vol01	406	167	578	1151
4	W0037_Vol02	144	62	250	456
5	W0037_Vol03	344	186	670	1200
6	W0041	1194	670	1668	3532
7	W0061	213	749	994	1956
8	W0076	628	209	854	1691
9	W0083	522	2230	1785	4537
10	W0106	1819	1858	3963	7640
	Total	8682	8503	14750	31935

The regex-based approach has contributed a significant amount of automatic abbreviation resolution. Adding more patterns will support the editors in the edition process saving them time and repetitive tasks.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

The project has published 28 works out of 116. Therefore, the constant research to improve automatic abbreviation resolution is one of the main tasks to meet these numbers. Combining different approaches, lists-based and regex-based approaches, has proved better results, yet there are improvement areas in sight.

One of them is improving word boundaries to cover abbreviations at the very beginning, very end of lines and hyphenated. Hyphenated abbreviations, are present in all texts in our corpus and are coded in TEI with attributes inside elements <pb/>, <cb/>, <lb/> (See Fig.1). Automatic abbreviation resolution in these cases is not yet covered, neither with the list-based nor with the regular expression-based approach. Since these cases also require extensive manual work, it is the target of future research.

Figure 1. Line with hyphenated abbreviation incōnventientes. Work: León Pinelo, Confirmaciones Reales de Encomiendas (2021 [1630]), in: The School of Salamanca. A Digital Collection of Sources

<<https://id.salamanca.school/texts/W0061>>
Folio 21v.

The lines in Fig.1 are coded in TEI as follows:

```
<lb/>començaron a experimentar cafi los mifmos incō-  
venientes<lb type="nb"/>en la quarta, aunque ya mas vencibles. I
```

Alternately, our constant growing abbreviation lists, and our patterns of the abbreviations utilized in the regex-based approach, could be the base to develop future suitable NLP tools to process early modern Latin and Spanish sources. Moreover, our full text data can provide suitable training data.

From another perspective, the implementation of regular expressions presented here can be adapted to structures and subsets of different natural languages to support editing processes in TEI format. Even the normalization and/or

processing of slang, online informal language or unstructured data.

6. References

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